

On Algebraic Multi-Vector Spaces

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Abstract: A Smarandache multi-space is a union of n spaces A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n with some additional conditions holding. Combining Smarandache multi-spaces with linear vector spaces in classical linear algebra, the conception of multi-vector spaces is introduced. Some characteristics of a multi-vector space are obtained in this paper.

Key words: vector, multi-space, multi-vector space, ideal subspace chain.

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1. Introduction

The notion of multi-spaces is introduced by Smarandache in [6] under his idea of hybrid mathematics: *combining different fields into a unifying field*([7]), which is defined as follows.

Definition 1.1 For any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ let A_i be a set with ensemble of law L_i , and the intersection of k sets $A_{i_1}, A_{i_2}, \dots, A_{i_k}$ of them constrains the law $I(A_{i_1}, A_{i_2}, \dots, A_{i_k})$. Then the union of $A_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$

$$\tilde{A} = \bigcup_{i=1}^n A_i$$

is called a *multi-space*.

As we known, a *vector space* or *linear space* consists of the following:

- (i) a field F of scalars;
- (ii) a set V of objects, called vectors;
- (iii) an operation, called vector addition, which associates with each pair of vectors \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} in V a vector $\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}$ in V , called the sum of \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , in such a way that
 - (1) addition is commutative, $\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{a}$;
 - (2) addition is associative, $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}) + \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{a} + (\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{c})$;
 - (3) there is a unique vector $\mathbf{0}$ in V , called the zero vector, such that $\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{a}$ for all \mathbf{a} in V ;
 - (4) for each vector \mathbf{a} in V there is a unique vector $-\mathbf{a}$ in V such that $\mathbf{a} + (-\mathbf{a}) = \mathbf{0}$;
- (iv) an operation \cdot , called scalar multiplication, which associates with each scalar k in F and a vector \mathbf{a} in V a vector $k \cdot \mathbf{a}$ in V , called the product of k with \mathbf{a} , in such a way that
 - (1) $1 \cdot \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}$ for every \mathbf{a} in V ;

- (2) $(k_1 k_2) \cdot \mathbf{a} = k_1(k_2 \cdot \mathbf{a})$;
- (3) $k \cdot (\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}) = k \cdot \mathbf{a} + k \cdot \mathbf{b}$;
- (4) $(k_1 + k_2) \cdot \mathbf{a} = k_1 \cdot \mathbf{a} + k_2 \cdot \mathbf{a}$.

We say that V is a *vector space over the field F* , denoted by $(V ; +, \cdot)$.

By combining Smarandache multi-spaces with linear spaces, a new kind of algebraic structure called multi-vector space is found, which is defined in the following.

Definition 1.2 Let $\tilde{V} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k V_i$ be a complete multi-space with binary operation set

$O(\tilde{V}) = \{(\dot{+}_i, \cdot_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ and $\tilde{F} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k F_i$ a multi-filed space with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{F}) = \{(+_i, \times_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq k\}$. If for any integers $i, j, 1 \leq i, j \leq k$ and $\forall \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c} \in \tilde{V}, k_1, k_2 \in \tilde{F}$,

(i) $(V_i; \dot{+}_i, \cdot_i)$ is a vector space on F_i with vector additive $\dot{+}_i$ and scalar multiplication \cdot_i ;

(ii) $(\mathbf{a} \dot{+}_i \mathbf{b}) \dot{+}_j \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{a} \dot{+}_i (\mathbf{b} \dot{+}_j \mathbf{c})$;

(iii) $(k_1 +_i k_2) \cdot_j \mathbf{a} = k_1 +_i (k_2 \cdot_j \mathbf{a})$;

if all those operation results exist, then \tilde{V} is called a multi-vector space on the multi-filed space \tilde{F} with a binary operation set $O(\tilde{V})$, denoted by $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$.

For subsets $\tilde{V}_1 \subset \tilde{V}$ and $\tilde{F}_1 \subset \tilde{F}$, if $(\tilde{V}_1; \tilde{F}_1)$ is also a multi-vector space, then call $(\tilde{V}_1; \tilde{F}_1)$ a multi-vector subspace of $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$.

The subject of this paper is to find some characteristics of a multi-vector space. For terminology and notation not defined here can be seen in [1], [3] for linear algebraic terminologies and in [2], [4] – [11] for multi-spaces and logics.

2. Characteristics of a multi-vector space

First, we have the following result for multi-vector subspace of a multi-vector space.

Theorem 2.1 For a multi-vector space $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$, $\tilde{V}_1 \subset \tilde{V}$ and $\tilde{F}_1 \subset \tilde{F}$, $(\tilde{V}_1; \tilde{F}_1)$ is a multi-vector subspace of $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$ if and only if for any vector additive $\dot{+}$, scalar multiplication \cdot in $(\tilde{V}_1; \tilde{F}_1)$ and $\forall \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \tilde{V}, \forall \alpha \in \tilde{F}$,

$$\alpha \cdot \mathbf{a} \dot{+} \mathbf{b} \in \tilde{V}_1$$

if their operation result exist.

Proof Denote by $\tilde{V} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k V_i, \tilde{F} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k F_i$. Notice that $\tilde{V}_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^k (\tilde{V}_1 \cap V_i)$. By definition, we know that $(\tilde{V}_1; \tilde{F}_1)$ is a multi-vector subspace of $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$ if and only if for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq k$, $(\tilde{V}_1 \cap V_i; \dot{+}_i, \cdot_i)$ is a vector subspace of $(V_i, \dot{+}_i, \cdot_i)$ and \tilde{F}_1 is a multi-filed subspace of \tilde{F} or $\tilde{V}_1 \cap V_i = \emptyset$.

According to the criterion for linear subspaces of a linear space ([3]), we know that for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq k$, $(\tilde{V}_1 \cap V_i; \dot{+}_i, \cdot_i)$ is a vector subspace of $(V_i, \dot{+}_i, \cdot_i)$ if and only if for $\forall \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \tilde{V}_1 \cap V_i, \alpha \in F_i$,

$$\alpha \cdot_i \mathbf{a} \dot{+}_i \mathbf{b} \in \tilde{V}_1 \cap V_i.$$

That is, for any vector additive $\dot{+}$, scalar multiplication \cdot in $(\tilde{V}_1; \tilde{F}_1)$ and $\forall \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \tilde{V}, \forall \alpha \in \tilde{F}$, if $\alpha \cdot \mathbf{a} \dot{+} \mathbf{b}$ exists, then $\alpha \cdot \mathbf{a} \dot{+} \mathbf{b} \in \tilde{V}_1$. \dagger

Corollary 2.1 *Let $(\tilde{U}; \tilde{F}_1), (\tilde{W}; \tilde{F}_2)$ be two multi-vector subspaces of a multi-vector space $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$. Then $(\tilde{U} \cap \tilde{W}; \tilde{F}_1 \cap \tilde{F}_2)$ is a multi-vector space.*

For a multi-vector space $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$, vectors $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n \in \tilde{V}$, if there are scalars $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n \in \tilde{F}$ such that

$$\alpha_1 \cdot_1 \mathbf{a}_1 \dot{+}_1 \alpha_2 \cdot_2 \mathbf{a}_2 \dot{+}_2 \dots \dot{+}_{n-1} \alpha_n \cdot_n \mathbf{a}_n = \mathbf{0},$$

where $\mathbf{0} \in \tilde{V}$ is a unit under an operation $\dot{+}$ in \tilde{V} and $\dot{+}_i, \cdot_i \in O(\tilde{V})$, then the vectors $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n$ are said to be *linearly dependent*. Otherwise, $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n$ to be *linearly independent*.

Notice that in a multi-vector space, there are two cases for linearly independent vectors $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n$:

(i) for any scalars $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n \in \tilde{F}$, if

$$\alpha_1 \cdot_1 \mathbf{a}_1 \dot{+}_1 \alpha_2 \cdot_2 \mathbf{a}_2 \dot{+}_2 \dots \dot{+}_{n-1} \alpha_n \cdot_n \mathbf{a}_n = \mathbf{0},$$

where $\mathbf{0}$ is a unit of \tilde{V} under an operation $\dot{+}$ in $O(\tilde{V})$, then $\alpha_1 = 0_{+1}, \alpha_2 = 0_{+2}, \dots, \alpha_n = 0_{+n}$, where $0_{+i}, 1 \leq i \leq n$ are the units under the operation $\dot{+}_i$ in \tilde{F} .

(ii) the operation result of $\alpha_1 \cdot_1 \mathbf{a}_1 \dot{+}_1 \alpha_2 \cdot_2 \mathbf{a}_2 \dot{+}_2 \dots \dot{+}_{n-1} \alpha_n \cdot_n \mathbf{a}_n$ does not exist.

Now for a subset $\hat{S} \subset \tilde{V}$, define its *linearly spanning set* $\langle \hat{S} \rangle$ to be

$$\langle \hat{S} \rangle = \{ \mathbf{a} \mid \mathbf{a} = \alpha_1 \cdot_1 \mathbf{a}_1 \dot{+}_1 \alpha_2 \cdot_2 \mathbf{a}_2 \dot{+}_2 \dots \in \tilde{V}, \mathbf{a}_i \in \hat{S}, \alpha_i \in \tilde{F}, i \geq 1 \}.$$

For a multi-vector space $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$, if there exists a subset $\hat{S}, \hat{S} \subset \tilde{V}$ such that $\tilde{V} = \langle \hat{S} \rangle$, then we say \hat{S} is a *linearly spanning set* of the multi-vector space \tilde{V} . If the vectors in a linearly spanning set \hat{S} of the multi-vector space \tilde{V} are linearly independent, then \hat{S} is said to be a *basis* of \tilde{V} .

Theorem 2.2 *Any multi-vector space $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$ has a basis.*

Proof Assume $\tilde{V} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k V_i, \tilde{F} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k F_i$ and the basis of the vector space $(V_i; \dot{+}_i, \cdot_i)$ is $\Delta_i = \{ \mathbf{a}_{i1}, \mathbf{a}_{i2}, \dots, \mathbf{a}_{in_i} \}, 1 \leq i \leq k$. Define

$$\widehat{\Delta} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k \Delta_i.$$

Then $\widehat{\Delta}$ is a linearly spanning set for \widetilde{V} by definition.

If vectors in $\widehat{\Delta}$ are linearly independent, then $\widehat{\Delta}$ is a basis of \widetilde{V} . Otherwise, choose a vector $\mathbf{b}_1 \in \widehat{\Delta}$ and define $\widehat{\Delta}_1 = \widehat{\Delta} \setminus \{\mathbf{b}_1\}$.

If we have obtained the set $\widehat{\Delta}_s$, $s \geq 1$ and it is not a basis, choose a vector $\mathbf{b}_{s+1} \in \widehat{\Delta}_s$ and define $\widehat{\Delta}_{s+1} = \widehat{\Delta}_s \setminus \{\mathbf{b}_{s+1}\}$.

If the vectors in $\widehat{\Delta}_{s+1}$ are linearly independent, then $\widehat{\Delta}_{s+1}$ is a basis of \widetilde{V} . Otherwise, we can define the set $\widehat{\Delta}_{s+2}$. Continue this process. Notice that for any integer i , $1 \leq i \leq k$, the vectors in Δ_i are linearly independent. Therefore, we can finally get a basis of \widetilde{V} . \spadesuit

Now we consider the finite-dimensional multi-vector space. A multi-vector space \widetilde{V} is *finite-dimensional* if it has a finite basis. By Theorem 2.2, if for any integer i , $1 \leq i \leq k$, the vector space $(V_i; +_i, \cdot_i)$ is finite-dimensional, then $(\widetilde{V}; \widetilde{F})$ is finite-dimensional. On the other hand, if there is an integer i_0 , $1 \leq i_0 \leq k$, such that the vector space $(V_{i_0}; +_{i_0}, \cdot_{i_0})$ is infinite-dimensional, then $(\widetilde{V}; \widetilde{F})$ is infinite-dimensional. This enables us to get the following corollary.

Corollary 2.2 *Let $(\widetilde{V}; \widetilde{F})$ be a multi-vector space with $\widetilde{V} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k V_i$, $\widetilde{F} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k F_i$. Then $(\widetilde{V}; \widetilde{F})$ is finite-dimensional if and only if for any integer i , $1 \leq i \leq k$, $(V_i; +_i, \cdot_i)$ is finite-dimensional.*

Theorem 2.3 *For a finite-dimensional multi-vector space $(\widetilde{V}; \widetilde{F})$, any two bases have the same number of vectors.*

Proof Let $\widetilde{V} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k V_i$ and $\widetilde{F} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k F_i$. The proof is by the induction on k . For $k = 1$, the assertion is true by Theorem 4 of Chapter 2 in [3].

For the case of $k = 2$, notice that by a result in linearly vector space theory (see also [3]), for two subspaces W_1, W_2 of a finite-dimensional vector space, if the basis of $W_1 \cap W_2$ is $\{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_t\}$, then the basis of $W_1 \cup W_2$ is

$$\{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_t, \mathbf{b}_{t+1}, \mathbf{b}_{t+2}, \dots, \mathbf{b}_{\dim W_1}, \mathbf{c}_{t+1}, \mathbf{c}_{t+2}, \dots, \mathbf{c}_{\dim W_2}\},$$

where, $\{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_t, \mathbf{b}_{t+1}, \mathbf{b}_{t+2}, \dots, \mathbf{b}_{\dim W_1}\}$ is a basis of W_1 and $\{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_t, \mathbf{c}_{t+1}, \mathbf{c}_{t+2}, \dots, \mathbf{c}_{\dim W_2}\}$ a basis of W_2 .

Whence, if $\widetilde{V} = W_1 \cup W_2$ and $\widetilde{F} = F_1 \cup F_2$, then the basis of \widetilde{V} is also

$$\{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_t, \mathbf{b}_{t+1}, \mathbf{b}_{t+2}, \dots, \mathbf{b}_{\dim W_1}, \mathbf{c}_{t+1}, \mathbf{c}_{t+2}, \dots, \mathbf{c}_{\dim W_2}\}.$$

Assume the assertion is true for $k = l$, $l \geq 2$. Now we consider the case of $k = l + 1$. In this case, since

$$\tilde{V} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^l V_i \right) \cup V_{l+1}, \quad \tilde{F} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^l F_i \right) \cup F_{l+1},$$

by the induction assumption, we know that any two bases of the multi-vector space $\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^l V_i; \bigcup_{i=1}^l F_i \right)$ have the same number p of vectors. If the basis of $\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^l V_i \right) \cap V_{l+1}$ is $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_n\}$, then the basis of \tilde{V} is

$$\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_n, \mathbf{f}_{n+1}, \mathbf{f}_{n+2}, \dots, \mathbf{f}_p, \mathbf{g}_{n+1}, \mathbf{g}_{n+2}, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{\dim V_{l+1}}\},$$

where $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_n, \mathbf{f}_{n+1}, \mathbf{f}_{n+2}, \dots, \mathbf{f}_p\}$ is a basis of $\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^l V_i; \bigcup_{i=1}^l F_i \right)$ and $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_n, \mathbf{g}_{n+1}, \mathbf{g}_{n+2}, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{\dim V_{l+1}}\}$ a basis of V_{l+1} . Whence, the number of vectors in a basis of \tilde{V} is $p + \dim V_{l+1} - n$ for the case $n = l + 1$.

Therefore, by the induction principle, we know the assertion is true for any integer k . \spadesuit

The number of a finite-dimensional multi-vector space \tilde{V} is called its *dimension*, denoted by $\dim \tilde{V}$.

Theorem 2.4 (dimensional formula) For a multi-vector space $(\tilde{V}; \tilde{F})$ with $\tilde{V} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k V_i$ and $\tilde{F} = \bigcup_{i=1}^k F_i$, the dimension $\dim \tilde{V}$ of \tilde{V} is

$$\dim \tilde{V} = \sum_{i=1}^k (-1)^{i-1} \sum_{\{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_i\} \subset \{1, 2, \dots, k\}} \dim(V_{i_1} \cap V_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap V_{i_i}).$$

Proof The proof is by induction on k . For $k = 1$, the formula is the trivial case of $\dim \tilde{V} = \dim V_1$. for $k = 2$, the formula is

$$\dim \tilde{V} = \dim V_1 + \dim V_2 - \dim(V_1 \cap V_2),$$

which is true by Theorem 6 of Chapter 2 in [3].

Now assume the formula is true for $k = n$. Consider the case of $k = n + 1$. According to the proof of Theorem 2.15, we know that

$$\begin{aligned} \dim \tilde{V} &= \dim \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n V_i \right) + \dim V_{n+1} - \dim \left(\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n V_i \right) \cap V_{n+1} \right) \\ &= \dim \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n V_i \right) + \dim V_{n+1} - \dim \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (V_i \cap V_{n+1}) \right) \\ &= \dim V_{n+1} + \sum_{i=1}^n (-1)^{i-1} \sum_{\{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_i\} \subset \{1, 2, \dots, n\}} \dim(V_{i_1} \cap V_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap V_{i_i}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \sum_{i=1}^n (-1)^{i-1} \sum_{\{i1, i2, \dots, ii\} \subset \{1, 2, \dots, n\}} \dim(V_{i1} \cap V_{i2} \cap \dots \cap V_{ii} \cap V_{n+1}) \\
& = \sum_{i=1}^n (-1)^{i-1} \sum_{\{i1, i2, \dots, ii\} \subset \{1, 2, \dots, k\}} \dim(V_{i1} \cap V_{i2} \cap \dots \cap V_{ii}).
\end{aligned}$$

By the induction principle, we know this formula is true for any integer k . \square

From Theorem 2.4, we get the following additive formula for any two multi-vector spaces.

Corollary 2.3(*additive formula*) For any two multi-vector spaces \tilde{V}_1, \tilde{V}_2 ,

$$\dim(\tilde{V}_1 \cup \tilde{V}_2) = \dim\tilde{V}_1 + \dim\tilde{V}_2 - \dim(\tilde{V}_1 \cap \tilde{V}_2).$$

3. Open problems for a multi-ring space

Notice that Theorem 2.3 has told us there is a similar linear theory for multi-vector spaces, but the situation is more complex. Here, we present some open problems for further research.

Problem 3.1 *Similar to linear spaces, define linear transformations on multi-vector spaces. Can we establish a new matrix theory for linear transformations?*

Problem 3.2 *Whether a multi-vector space must be a linear space?*

Conjecture A *There are non-linear multi-vector spaces in multi-vector spaces.*

Based on Conjecture A, there is a fundamental problem for multi-vector spaces.

Problem 3.3 *Can we apply multi-vector spaces to non-linear spaces?*

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